

Localization Documentation

Annabichl No. 4

vulgo Michitz

INITIAL SITUATION

Source: Klagenfurter Zeitung, 1844

Content: Mention of the address „Annabichl Nr. 4“

Question: *Existence and location of this house or farmstead*

EVIDENCE OF THE FARMSTEAD AND BASIS OF THE ASSIGNMENT

The farmstead is repeatedly documented in the parish registers of St. Georgen am Sandhof. In the parcel protocol of the Franciscan Cadastre, it is recorded under the vulgo name “**Michitz**”; the variant “Michiz” also appears in other sources. Further mentions are found in historical newspaper articles.

The assignment of the building parcel is based on the Franciscan Cadastre and the Digital Cadastral Map (BEV); the positioning in the present-day landscape is carried out using KAGIS.

Note: *The localization refers exclusively to the historical site of the farmstead. The building had already disappeared before 1952.*

RESULT OF THE LOCALIZATION

The historical farmstead could be clearly localized.

Location	Klagenfurt-Annabichl, cadastral municipality Ehrental
Position	Henriquezweg / Alleegasse
Coordinates	E 14.311542° / N 46.654548°
Status	<i>Farmstead disappeared — no building remains</i>

HISTORICAL STATE CA. 1828

In the Franciscan Cadastre, a single rectangular residential building of non-masonry construction with a ground area of approximately 83 m² (approx. 23 square klafter) is recorded for the farmstead. For comparable residential buildings of this period, timber or mixed construction can generally be assumed based on building-historical evidence. The farmstead was located in a loosely scattered settlement south of Annabichl Castle. From the associated parcel protocols and further historical evidence, an affiliation with the settlement structure surrounding the castle can be derived.

Map source:
KAGIS – Carinthian Geographic Information System, State of Carinthia, Franciscan Cadastre ca. 1828 (accessed 2 April 2026)
<https://kagis.ktn.gv.at>

Cartographic processing and interpretation by Brigitta Szekely.

CURRENT STATE

The historical location today lies within the area of the Ehrentalerberg tunnel (A2). No building remains; no address is assigned anymore. The original building parcel was transferred into several land register units (EZ). Within a radius of approximately 100 m, there are now individual detached houses along Henriquezweg, infrastructure facilities, and industrial buildings.

Map source:
KAGIS – Carinthian Geographic Information System, State of Carinthia, current topographic map (accessed 2 April 2026)
<https://kagis.ktn.gv.at/>

Cartographic processing and interpretation by Brigitta Szekely.

FURTHER ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH POTENTIAL

A building and the corresponding address could be clearly documented and localized at this site in the consulted sources from the late 18th century until approximately 1925. Since at least 1952, the building has disappeared.

Further analysis, particularly regarding ownership sequences or construction phases, is not part of this brief study but can readily be expanded based on the available data.

SOURCES

The listed sources represent selected evidence and form the basis of the present localization.

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| 1 | Klagenfurter Zeitung, 1844 | <i>anno.onb.ac.at</i> |
| 2 | Parish registers St. Georgen am Sandhof | <i>matricula-online.at</i> |
| 3 | Franciscan Cadastre including parcel protocol | <i>Carinthian State Archives (KLA)</i> |
| 4 | Digital Cadastral Map Austria (BEV) | <i>bev.gv.at</i> |
| 5 | KAGIS — Carinthian Geographic Information System | <i>kagis.ktn.gv.at</i> |

The present documentation is intended as an exemplary application of a methodologically traceable localization of historical houses or farmsteads.